

Impact of Deborah number on heat and mass transfer analysis over a stretching sheet

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Abstract

The Buongiorno model Maxwell nanofluid stream, heat and mass exchange qualities over an extending sheet is mathematically researched in this examination. This model is incorporating the effects of Brownian motion and thermophoresis. The overseeing fractional differential conditions are changed into coupled nonlinear common differential condition by utilizing comparability change strategy. The resultant nonlinear differential conditions are settled by utilizing Limited component strategy. The sketches of velocity, temperature and concentration with diverse values of Brownian motion parameter, thermophoretic parameter, Deborah number, Prandtl number and Lewis number have investigated and are depicted through plots. Moreover, the values of Nusselt number, Skin-friction co-efficient and Sherwood numbers are also computed and are shown in tables.

Keywords: Maxwell nanofluid; Thermophoresis; Finite Element Method; Brownian motion.

1.Introduction

Nanofluids can be utilized as one kind of improved warm properties as new collants in heat move gear like electronic cooling framework, heat exchangers and radiators. Numerous writing audit shows that there are different kinds of nanofluids suspensions to break down about heat move attributes over various calculations, but there are numerous helpful for their controlled optical properties. Nanofluids have been found to have improved

thermo actual properties, for example, warm diffusivity, consistency, warm conductivity and convective intensity move coefficients contrasted with based liquids. Because of the liberal wellsprings of broad dispersal of battery worked gadgets and clean energy, for example, workstations, PDAs have emphasized the need for a shrewd mechanical treatment of fiery assets. Nanofluids have been demonstrated to be able to handle this role in some instances as a smart fluid. Choi et al. [1] have investigated the anomalous phenomena to systematic thermal conductivity with nanotube-in-oil and remarked that strengthened of thermal conductivity is higher than other nanostructured material dispersed in fluids. Ghalambaz et al. [2] discussed the characteristics of heat and mass transfer of nanofluids which are made up of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles and water as base fluid embedded with porous media over vertical cone. Several authors [3 – 10] professed that the sway of different parameters on heat and mass transfer characteristics of nanofluid over the different geometries.

In ongoing examinations, the investigation of normal convection stream of nanofluids have broad scope of uses in various regions like designing and science, cooling and warming, raw petroleum extraction, heat exchangers, streamlined geothermal framework and so forth, Scientists carried out another method to work on warm conductivity by adding nanoparticles to general fluids called as nanofluids. The progression of non-Newtonian liquids is driving edge in the new region in view of its wide reach applications. The uses of non-Newtonian liquids in the different regions like natural sciences, geophysics, petrol and compound businesses. By and large non Newtonian liquids can be grouped into 3 kinds, for example, differential sort, rate type and basic sort. The sub class of rate kind of non-Newtonian liquid can be considered as Maxwell nanofluid. Great number of articles on intensity and mass exchange stream of Maxwell nanofluid over extending sheet are taken note in literature. Nadeem et al. [11] deliberated the behavior of MHD boundary layer flow of Maxwell nanofluid over a stretching sheet with Buongiorno model and reported that the local

Nusselt number decelerates with greater values of N_b . Bai et al. [12] implemented Buongiorno model to investigate the heat and mass transfer flow of Maxwell nanofluid over stretching sheet and conclude that fluid flow velocity and rate of velocity degenerates with rising values of Maxwell parameter. Hayat et al. [13] presented optimal homotopic scheme method to analyze heat and mass transfer rotating flow of Maxwell liquid over a exponentially stretching sheet and reported that thickness of boundary layer and temperature of the fluid escalates with increasing values of local Deborah number. Muhammed et al. [14] have studied Buongiorno's mathematical model Maxwell nanomaterial flow saturating a non-Darcy porous medium over stretching surface and identified that enhancement in the temperature and concentration profiles with intensifying values of Deborah number. Majeed et al. [15] perceived the sway of non-linear thermal radiation on Maxwell nanofluid flow, heat and mass transfer characteristics over elongating cylinder and reported that the effects of non-linear thermal radiation provides better heat transfer rate at the surface of cylinder compared to problem in the presence of linear thermal radiation. The effects of activation energy and non-linear thermal radiation on boundary layer Darcy-Forchheimer flow of Maxwell nanofluid over stretching sheet discussed by Sajid et al. [16]. Shenet al. [17] introduced the nanoparticle shape to study fractional Maxwell viscoelastic nanofluid. Cattaneo heat flux model is applied to construct the mathematical problem to investigate the unsteady flow and heat transfer characteristics of Maxwell "nanofluid over a vertical plate and observed that Nusselt number escalates with intensifying values of magnetic field parameter. Khan et al. [18] reviewed the sway of electric field and magnetic field on unsteady flow of Maxwell nanofluid over a stretching surface in the presence of thermal radiation and determined that concentration profile decelerates with higher values of Schmidt number. Khan et al. [19] identified temperature profile diminishes with enhanced values of Deborah number in their study on heat and mass transfer analysis of Maxwell nanofluid over a

stretched cylinder in the presence of heat source/sink and thermal radiation. Irfan et al. [20] implemented Homotopic analysis method to determine the impact of magnetic field and chemical reaction on flow, heat and mass transfer characteristics of Buongiorno's model Maxwell nanofluid over a stretching cylinder and stated that local Nusselt number declines with improving values of thermophoretic number. Ijaz et al. [21] perceived heat and mass transfer nonlinearly convective flow of Buongiorno's model Maxwell nanofluid flow over stretched inclined cylinder by taking Brownian motion and thermophoresis into the account and noticed velocity profile declines with intensified values of Deborah number. Ahmed et al. [22, 23] presented numerical solution for MHD boundary layer flow, mass and heat transfer characteristics of Buongiorno model Maxwell nanofluid over rotating disk and vertical stretching cylinder. Khan et al. [24] detected that deterioration in the Skin friction coefficient, Nusselt number, Sherwood number and microorganism number with improving values of thermal relaxation parameter in the study of heat and mass transfer analysis of unsteady flow of bio convective Maxwell nanofluid flow over exponentially stretching sheet. Jamshed et al. [25] discussed entropy generation, flow and heat transfer features of Maxwell nanofluid over an infinite horizontal surface in the presence of magnetic field and thermal radiation. Furthermore, they found that the entropy generation elaborates as the values of nanoparticle volume fraction parameter upgrades.

In present days, the study of natural convection of Maxwell nanofluid in the presence of convective boundary conditions over different geometries has received much priority by research community. Jusoh et al. [26] reviewed numerical solution to examine fluid flow and heat transfer features of MHD boundary layer 3D Maxwell nanofluid over a stretching/shrinking surface with convective boundary conditions and found that the value of Nusselt number intensified as the values of Prandtl number upsurges. Muhammad et al. [27] professed that fluid flow, heat transfer analysis of Buongiorno model Maxwell nanofluid flow

over linear stretching surface subject to convective boundary conditions and determined that both temperature and concentration profiles upsurges with intensifying values of Biot number. Mahanthesh et al. [28] premeditated the combined effect of nonlinear thermal radiation and convection on MHD boundary layer heat transfer analysis of non-Newtonian Maxwell nanofluid induced by the stretching of a flat plate in two lateral directions under the convective boundary condition. They conclude that the effect of temperature profile is stronger for the case of solar radiation compare to without radiation. The steady of MHD flow, heat transfer features of a Maxwell nanofluid over stretched cylinder in the presence of convective boundary conditions has been investigated by Irfan et al. [29] and they determined that velocity profile declines with higher values of magnetic field parameter. Koteswara Reddy et al. [30] investigated the sway of convective boundary condition on mass and heat transfer analysis of non-homogenous Buongiorno's model MHD Maxwell, Oldroyd-B nanofluid and Jeffery nanofluid over cone with heat source/sink. Furthermore, they reported that mass and heat transfer rates are more significant in Jeffery nanofluid than other two Maxwell and Oldroyd B nanofluids. Sajid et al. [31] perceived heat and mass transfer analysis of Maxwell nanofluid over a linear stretching surface in the presence of nonlinear thermal radiation and detected that temperature variations boosted with increasing values of thermophoresis and radiation parameter. Hayat et al. [32] reviewed the effect of thermal radiation, double stratification and convective conditions on mixed convection flow of Maxwell nanofluid over stretching surface. MHD boundary layer heat and mass transfer analysis Maxwell nanofluid under the convective boundary condition has been presented by Khan et al. [33 & 34]. Rashid et al. [35] demonstrated that the sway of the thermal radiation and heat source/sink on mass and heat transfer analysis of non-Newtonian Buongiorno's Maxwell nanofluid over stretching cylinder and reported that temperature fields enhances with escalate values of thermal Biot number and radiation parameter. Waqas et al. [36]

described theoretical analysis of flow heat, mass transfer features of Maxwell nanofluid over a stretching surface in the presence of gyrotactic microorganism. The study of MHD boundary layer flow and heat transfer analysis of Maxwell nanofluid over Riga surface has been deliberated by Ramesh et al. [37].

After mindful perception of above examinations we start that no investigations have been uncovered at this point to consider an investigation of Buongiorno model nanofluid mass and intensity highlights over an extending sheet with convective limit conditions. Exceptional endeavors have been assumed the effect of thermophoresis, Brownian movement on stream field, temperature and fixation representations, Skin friction coefficient, Nusselt number and Sherwood numbers. In like manner, trail is made to examine above research in this article.

2. Mathematical Analysis:

We consider three dimensional, steady, incompressible MHD, heat and mass transfer boundary layer flow of non-Newtonian Maxwell nanofluid over a stretching sheet under convective boundary conditions as illustrated in Fig. 1. Here the flow is caused by a stretching surface at $z = 0$. The thermophoresis and Brownian motion have been contemplated in this problem. It is assumed that T_w , to be determined, is the result of connective heating process which is characterized by a temperature T_f and heat transfer coefficient h_f , and C_w is the nanoparticle volume fraction at the surface of the cone and T_∞ and C_∞ are the temperature and nanoparticle volume fraction of the ambient fluid, respectively. An external magnetic field of strength B_0 is applied in the direction of the y –axis. The governing boundary layer expressions in the Maxwell nanofluid with heat and mass transfer can be expressed as follows:

Fig. 1.Schematic diagram of the problem.

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$\left(u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right) + \lambda_1 \left(u^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + v^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + w^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} + 2uv \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} + 2vw \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y \partial z} + 2uw \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} \right) = v \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} + g [\beta(T - T_\infty) + \beta^*(C - C_\infty)] \tag{2}$$

$$\left(u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \right) + \lambda_1 \left(u^2 \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + v^2 \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + w^2 \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial z^2} + 2uv \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y} + 2vw \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y \partial z} - 2uv \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y} \right) = v \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial z^2} + g [\beta(T - T_\infty) + \beta^*(C - C_\infty)] \tag{3}$$

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \tau \left[D_B \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \left(\frac{D_T}{T_\infty} \right) \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right] \tag{4}$$

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} = D_B \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} + \left(\frac{D_T}{T_\infty} \right) \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \tag{5}$$

The associated boundary conditions are

$$u = ax, \quad v = 0, \quad T = T_w, \quad C = C_w \quad \text{at} \quad z = 0 \tag{6}$$

$$u \rightarrow 0, \quad T \rightarrow T_\infty, \quad C \rightarrow C_\infty \quad \text{at} \quad z \rightarrow \infty \tag{7}$$

We now introduce the following similarity variables to transform the governing equations into system of ordinary differential equations:

$$u = axf'(\eta), \quad v = ayg'(\eta), \quad w = -(ay)^{\frac{1}{2}}(f(\eta) + g(\eta)), \quad \theta(\eta) = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty}, \quad S(\eta) = \frac{C - C_\infty}{C_w - C_\infty}$$

$$\eta = \left(\frac{a}{\nu} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} z \tag{8}$$

Using above similarity variables the Eqns. (1) – (5), we obtain the following non – linear ordinary differential equations

$$f'''' + (f + g)f'' - f'^2 + \beta(2(f + g)f'f'' - (f + g)^2 f''') + [\theta + Nr S] = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$g'''' + (f + g)f'' - g'^2 + \beta(2(f + g)f'f'' - (f + g)^2 g''') + [\theta + Nr S] = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\theta'' + Pr (f + g)\theta' + Nb \theta' S' + Nt(\theta')^2 = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$S'' + Le (f + g) S' + \frac{Nt}{Nb} \theta'' = 0 \quad (12)$$

The transformed boundary conditions are

$$\eta = 0, \quad f' = 1, \quad \theta = 1, \quad S = 1.$$

$$\eta \rightarrow \infty, \quad f' \rightarrow 0, \quad \theta \rightarrow 0, \quad S \rightarrow 0. \quad (13)$$

where, prime denotes differentiation with respect to η , and the significant thermophysical parameters dictating the flow dynamics are defined by

$$\beta = \lambda_1 a, \quad Nb = \frac{\tau_{DB}(C_w - C_\infty)}{\alpha}, \quad Nt = \frac{\tau_{DT}(T_w - T_\infty)}{\alpha T_\infty}, \quad Le = \frac{\gamma}{D_B}, \quad Pr = \frac{\gamma}{\alpha}, \quad B1 = \frac{h_f}{k \left(\frac{a}{\gamma}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (14)$$

Quantities of practical interest in this problem are the skin-friction coefficient (C_f), local Nusselt number (Nu_x), and the local Sherwood number (Sh_x), which are defined as

$$C_f = \frac{2 \tau_w}{\rho}, \quad Nu_x = \frac{x q_w}{k(T_w - T_\infty)}, \quad Sh_x = \frac{x J_w}{D_B(c_w - c_\infty)} \quad (15)$$

3. NUMERICAL METHOD OF SOLUTION

The finite element method (FEM) is such a powerful method for solving ordinary differential equations and partial differential equations. The basic idea of this method is dividing the whole domain into smaller elements of finite dimensions called finite elements. This method is such a good numerical method in modern engineering analysis, and it can be applied for solving integral equations including heat transfer, fluid mechanics, chemical processing, electrical systems, and many other fields. The steps involved in the finite element method [38 – 40] are as follows.

- (i) *Finite-element discretization*
- (ii) *Generation of the element equations*
- (iii) *Assembly of element equations*
- (iv) *Imposition of boundary conditions*
- (v) *Solution of assembled equations*

4. Results and Discussion.

The numerical results describing the radial and axial velocity, temperature and concentration behavior of a suspension containing nanoparticles and skin friction coefficient, Nusselt number and Sherwood number are presented in this paper. The sway of pertinent parameters on fluid flow, heat and mass transfer characteristics of Maxwell nanofluids are analyzed in Figs. 2 – 15. The obtained results are compared with existing results of Hayat et al. [41] and shown Table 1. Mesh independency test with quadratic shape function and boundary layer thickness (η) is depicted in Table 2. Tables 3 and 4 reveal that the required convergence of the present problem is achieved at the element size 0.01 with $\eta = 4$ for velocity, concentration and $\eta = 6$ for temperature of the nanofluid.

Figs. 2 – 5 depict the sway of Deborah number (β) on both radial and axial velocity, temperature and concentration portraits of Maxwell nanofluids. It is perceived that both radial and axial velocity distributions shrink with up surging values of Deborah number (β). However, the temperature distributions developed with increment values of (β). But there is quite opposite trend is happen in concentration distributions. This is due to the fact that Deborah number is depending on relaxation time, as the Deborah number raises the relaxation time of the Maxwell nanofluid increases which causes the declination in the velocity profile as well as temperature profile optimizes.

The sketches of temperature and concentration fields with increased values of Brownian motion parameter (N_b) in the flow region are depicted in Figs. 6 – 7. The

temperature sketches elaborated with step up values of (Nb) , while, the concentration sketches diminishes as the values of (Nb) developed. This is owing fact that due to the Brownian motion nanoparticles explored in the base fluid persuaded by the motion of particles and it moves from hot surface area and related to the size and agglomeration of nanoparticles.

It is perceived that from Fig. 8 – 9 both temperature and concentration portraits escalates with an improving values of thermophoretic parameter (Nt) . Due to the thermophoretic forces the particles present in the base fluid creates hot surfaces in boundary layer. Hence, this force develops both temperature and concentration of Maxwell nanofluid in the entire fluid flow region.

The influence of Lewis number (Le) on solutal boundary layer flow is depicted in Fig.10. It is cognized that concentration profiles of Maxwell nanofluid slackens with step-up values of (Le) . Figs. 11 reveals the sway of Prandtl number (Pr) on temperature sketches of Maxwell nanofluid. It is detected that intensification in temperature profile with step up values of (Pr) .

The impact of Buoyancy ratio parameter (Nr) on the profiles of radial and axial velocity, temperature and concentration is depicted in Figs. 12 – 15. It is noticed from Fig. 20 and 21 that the radial velocity of the nanofluid deteriorates, however, axial velocity profiles intensifies in the fluid region with up surging values of (Nr) . Temperature of the nanofluid augments, whereas, concentration of the nanofluid diminishes with rising values of (Nr) .

The values of local Skin-friction coefficient (C_f) , Nusselt number (Nu_x) and Sherwood number (Sh_x) of Maxwell nanofluid for dissimilar values of pertinent parameters are noticed in Table 3 and 4. It is concluded that the dimensionless rates of velocity and rates of mass transfer of Maxwell nanofluid escalates with respect to the intensifying values of (β) . However, non-dimensional heat transfer rate decelerates with improving values of (β) . It is

reported that rate of velocity and rate of temperature values upsurges, however, rate of concentration values are worsen with enhanced values of (Pr). It is estimated that diminution of Skin-friction coefficient and Nusselt number with elaborated values of (Nb). It is apparent that reverse trend is happened that the value of (C_f), (Nu_x) and (Sh_x) with an increasing values of (Nt). Finally, up surging values of (Le) diminishes the Skin-friction coefficient number and Nusselt number, whereas, Sherwood number step-ups with an incorporating values of (Le). The non-dimensional rates of velocity and Sherwood number values intensifies, however, Nusselt number values deteriorates with buoyancy ratio parameter (Nr).

5. Conclusion.

The numerical study of Buongiorno's model Maxwell nanofluid velocity, temperature and concentration behavior over a stretching sheet with magnetic field and thermal radiation are analyzed and the outcomes are depicted through graphs in this analysis. The consequent nonlinear differential equations are solved numerically by using Finite Element method. The skin-friction co-efficient, Nusselt number and Sherwood numbers are also evaluated and shown in tables. The following noticeable points in this analysis are reviewed.

- (i) Rate of velocity and rate of heat transfer of Maxwell nanofluid augments with enhanced values of (Nt). However, rate mass transfer diminutions as values of (Nt) rises.
- (ii) The temperature distributions of Maxwell nanofluid decelerates with higher values of (Pr). Whereas, the reverse trend is happened in the concentration sketches with respect to the higher values of (Pr).
- (iii) The velocity and concentration dispersals of Maxwell nanofluid slackens as values of (β) enhances.
- (iv) The values of (C_f) and (Nu_x) of Maxwell nanofluids deteriorates with augmented values of (Le).

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Table 1. Comparison of $(-\theta'(0))$ for $Pr = 0.7$ and fixed other parameters.

Parameter		$(-\theta'(0))$	
Nt	Nb	Hayat et al. [41]	Present Study
0.0	0.5	0.7451	0.7448
0.5	0.5	0.7247	0.7242
1.0	0.5	0.7045	0.7049
0.1	0.5	0.7408	0.7405
0.1	1.0	0.7408	0.7406
0.1	1.5	0.7408	0.7404

Table 2: Mesh independency test with quadratic shape function and boundary layer thickness (η).

η	Element Size	$(-f''(0))$	$(-\theta'(0))$	$(-S'(0))$
2	0.1	0.711523	0.636658	0.963883
	0.05	0.711535	0.636721	0.963912
	0.025	0.711546	0.636832	0.963926
	0.01	0.711553	0.636865	0.963938
	0.005	0.711559	0.636867	0.963939
4	0.1	0.711519	0.636728	0.963884
	0.05	0.711527	0.636742	0.963913
	0.025	0.711534	0.636758	0.963927
	0.01	0.711541	0.636777	0.963938
	0.005	0.711548	0.636792	0.963939
6	0.1	0.711514	0.636724	0.963889
	0.05	0.711522	0.636739	0.963922
	0.025	0.711531	0.636758	0.963924
	0.01	0.711535	0.636762	0.963927
	0.005	0.711539	0.636769	0.963929
	0.1	0.711511	0.636718	---

8	0.05	0.711518	0.636726	---
	0.025	0.711523	0.636739	---
	0.01	0.711526	0.636742	---
	0.005	0.711526	0.636746	---

Table 3: Values of Skin friction coefficient ($-f''(0)$), local Nusselt number ($-\theta'(0)$) and local Sherwood number ($-S'(0)$).

Parameters		$-f''(0)$	$-\theta'(0)$	$-S'(0)$
β	Pr			
0.0	0.7	0.81254	0.62671	0.96425
0.04	0.7	0.81478	0.62381	0.97485
0.07	0.7	0.82915	0.62056	0.98623
0.1	0.7	0.83014	0.61740	0.99712
0.1	0.7	0.93568	0.63900	0.95758
0.1	0.8	0.96581	0.69013	0.82213
0.1	0.9	0.98412	0.73896	0.68866
0.1	1.0	1.02214	0.78588	0.55694

Table 4: Values of skin-friction coefficient ($-f''(0)$), local Nusselt number ($-\theta'(0)$) and local Sherwood number ($-S'(0)$).

Parameters				$-f''(0)$	$-\theta'(0)$	$-S'(0)$
Nb	Nt	Le	Nr			
0.1	0.5	2.0	0.5	1.14157	0.60204	2.01354
0.2	0.5	2.0	0.5	1.11602	0.57231	2.11902
0.3	0.5	2.0	0.5	1.07451	0.56217	2.21473
0.4	0.5	2.0	0.5	0.96026	0.54182	2.31879
0.1	0.3	2.0	0.5	0.89002	0.67337	1.31579
0.1	0.4	2.0	0.5	0.90498	0.65581	1.21786
0.1	0.5	2.0	0.5	0.91728	0.63918	0.91493
0.1	0.6	2.0	0.5	0.93209	0.62282	0.82148
0.1	0.5	1.5	0.5	1.11625	0.61290	0.60125
0.1	0.5	2.0	0.5	1.08295	0.61740	0.98126
0.1	0.5	2.5	0.5	1.05806	0.61976	1.30148

0.1	0.5	3.0	0.5	1.04028	0.62113	1.58381
0.1	0.5	2.0	0.1	0.29911	0.65971	0.93171
0.1	0.5	2.0	0.4	0.24610	0.64435	0.95091
0.1	0.5	2.0	0.7	0.20781	0.62796	0.97136
0.1	0.5	2.0	1.0	0.81946	0.61051	0.99307

Fig.2. The effect of (β) on Radial velocity profiles.

Fig.3. The effect of (β) on Axial velocity profiles.

Fig.4. The effect of (β) on Temperature profiles.

Fig.5. The effect of (β) on Concentration profiles.

Fig.6. The effect of (Nb) on Temperature profiles.

Fig.7. The effect of (Nb) on Concentration profiles.

Fig.8. The effect of (Nt) on Temperature profiles.

Fig.9. The effect of (Nt) on Concentration profiles.

Fig.10. The Effect of (Le) on Concentration profile

Fig.11. The Effect of (Cr) on Concentration profile.

Fig.12. The effect of (Nr) on Radial Velocity profiles.

Fig.13. The effect of (Nr) on axial velocity profiles.

